

Ambulatory Surgeries: Modern Era of Surgical Practice**Aman Sharma¹, Manjul Mohan², Sharad Seth³, Mohit Biswas⁴**¹Junior Resident, Department of Surgery Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh India²Professor, Department of Surgery Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh India³Professor and HOD, Department of Surgery Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh India⁴Assistant professor, General Surgery Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Rohilkhand Medical College Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Ambulatory surgery stands as a vital component within global healthcare systems, offering patients elective procedures with discharge within 72 hours. It serves as a crucial link between inpatient and outpatient surgeries, fueled by technological advancements, patient preferences for shorter hospital stays, and cost-effective healthcare delivery models. The approach yields benefits such as reduced complications; shorter hospital stays, and improved resource allocation.

Aim: To assess the feasibility, benefits, and complications associated with ambulatory surgeries.

Objective: To Evaluate acceptability and practicality of ambulatory surgery

- Safety of the patients
- Different types of ambulatory surgeries
- Post-operative complications
- Readmissions
- Safety of the patients

Methods: It was an observational study done in the department of the general surgery in Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly from 1 December 2022 to 31 November 2023. The study analyzed data from 360 adult patients undergoing various types of ambulatory surgeries over one year.

Result: The mean age of the patients was 39.74 years, with an almost equal distribution of males (51%) and females (49%). Overall, 8% of patients experienced postoperative complications, with only 2.2% requiring extended hospital stays (>72 hours). Surgical complications accounted for 68% of total complications, while anesthesia-related complications constituted 32%.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the study indicates that ambulatory surgeries are safe, beneficial, and feasible, with minimal mortality and a low rate of extended hospital stays and unplanned readmissions. Nevertheless, challenges persist, including patient selection appropriateness and post-operative complications. Addressing these hurdles demands multidisciplinary collaboration, standardized guidelines, and comprehensive care strategies. Key elements encompass preoperative evaluations, patient education, and postoperative monitoring. Advancing ambulatory surgery necessitates on-going research, exploring regional and institutional nuances to refine patient identification, post-operative care, and overall satisfaction. With dedicated efforts for continuous improvement, healthcare systems can harness the advantages of ambulatory surgery while effectively managing its challenges, ultimately enhancing patient outcomes and system-wide efficiency.

Keywords: Ambulatory surgeries, post-operative complication, ERAS protocol, Day care surgeries, minimally invasive surgeries, Office surgeries, Biopsies.

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Introduction

Ambulatory surgery refers to elective procedures where patients are admitted and discharged within 72 hours, ensuring proper facilities and safety as per clinical standards. These surgeries can take place in clinics, health centers, or hospitals and

encompass various terms like outpatient surgery, same-day surgery, and short-stay surgery. Distinguishing ambulatory surgery from inpatient and outpatient procedures is essential, as inpatient surgeries require longer hospital stays, while outpa-

tient procedures typically involve same-day admissions without overnight stays. [1,2] Ambulatory surgery includes more complex interventions than standard outpatient procedures and necessitates specialized equipment and surgical teams, along with rigorous pre-operative, intraoperative, and post-operative protocols. The growth of ambulatory surgery has been fueled by advances in minimally invasive techniques, anesthesia, and perioperative care, along with a shift towards cost-effective healthcare solutions.[3] The American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) classification system aids in selecting suitable candidates based on health status, optimizing safety and outcomes. While ambulatory surgeries offer benefits like reduced recovery times and lower complication rates, challenges such as patient selection and potential complications must be addressed to ensure effective implementation. A multidisciplinary approach and stringent guidelines can enhance patient safety and satisfaction in this expanding field. [4]

Material and Method

Place of Study: This study was carried out in department of General Surgery, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh

Type of Study: Observational study

Time of Study: 1st November 2022 to 31st October 2023

Study Duration: 1 year.

Subjects: All adult patients.

Sample Size: In our study a total of 359 patients were taken Sample size has been calculated using formula $n = 4 p q / L^2$ p: 66 q: q=100-p (34) L: Allowable error (5%). [5]

Statistical Analysis:

The data was entered in the SPSS (Statistical Package for social sciences) licensed version 23.0. Descriptive analysis was done by calculating proportions, means & standard deviation. Appropriate statistical test was applied depending on type & the distribution and type of data. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. OPD/Office procedures.
2. Underwent surgical intervention and were discharged within 72 hours of admission
3. All adult patients
4. American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) class I (normal healthy patients) and class II (patients with mild systemic disease) patients.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Surgery requiring more than 2 hours
2. Surgery with anticipation of major fluid loss / blood loss.
3. Patient living far and not easily reachable or able to transport easily / difficult access to the house.
4. Mentally retarded/ unstable psychiatric illness
5. Proper care givers were not available at home
6. Medically unfit for early discharge
7. History of angina at rest, MI, severe hepatic disease or any other chronic health illness which can delay the discharge of the patient.

Intervention/Procedure:

- Office surgery/procedure room surgeries (Not admitted)
- Day care surgeries (Admitted and will be discharged within 12 hours of admitted)
- Overnight stay surgeries (Admitted and will be discharged within 23 hours of admission)
- Short stay surgeries (Admitted and will be discharged within 72 hours of admission)

Discharge Criteria:

- Vitals stable
- Correct orientation as to time place person
- Accepting oral feeds
- Adequate pain control with oral analgesics
- Minimal nausea and vomiting
- Minimal bleeding/wound drainage
- Written and verbal instructions given about postoperative care
- Knows when to come back for follow up
- Emergency contact/SOS details

Observations

Table 1: Different Types of Ambulatory Surgeries

Type of ambulatory Surgeries	No. of patients	Percentage
Office surgery	106	29%
Daycare Surgery	104	29%
Overnight surgery	42	12%
Short stay surgery	100	28%

Table 2: On the basis of post-operative complication rates patients are divided

	No. of patients	Percentage
Post-operative complications	28	8%
Patients without any Post-operative complications	333	92%

Table 3: Types of complications

Complications	Percentage
Surgical	68%
Anaesthetics	32%

Table 4: Different types of post-operative complications

Post-operative complication	No. of patients	%
Nausea and vomiting	5	17%
Surgical site pain	10	35%
Bleeding	4	14%
Hematuria	4	14%
Wound dehiscence	1	4%
Headache	3	10%
Backache	1	3%

Table 5: Patients are divided on the basis of Hospital stay

Hospital stay	No. Of Patients	%
Extended Stay (>72hours)	7	1.94%
Delayed discharge (<72 hours)	23	6.40%

Table 6: Different causes for extended hospital stay (>72hours)

Reason for extended stay (>72hours)	No. of patients	%
Wound dehiscence	1	14.2%
Extensive surgery	2	28.57%
Post-operative nausea vomiting	2	28.57%
Drowsiness	2	28.57%

Table 7: Reasons for delayed discharge (hospital stay <72hours)

Reason for Delayed discharge (<72hours of hospital stay)	No. of patients	%
Observation	3	13.04%
Bleeding	1	4.34%
Extensive surgery	1	4.34%
Far off Distance to home	10	43.4%
Change of anaesthesia	2	8.69%
Patients demand	4	17.39%
Pain	1	4.39%
Hematuria	1	4.39%

Table 8: shows Total no. of Readmissions and reason for Readmission

	No. of patients	Percentage
Readmission	6	2%

Table 9: shows Total no. of Readmissions and reason for Readmission

Reason for readmission	No. of Patients	%
Bleeding	1	0.27%
Hematuria	2	0.55%
Wound Dehiscence	2	0.55%
Nausea & Vomiting	1	0.27%

Results

1. In our study 359 patients underwent ambulatory surgery.
2. The patients under American society of anesthesia grade I were 84% and the patients under American society of anesthesia grade II were 16%. There was no significant difference

in the complication rates of either of two groups. ($p=0.813307$)

3. The Maximum number of patients in the ambulatory surgery setting was operated under local anesthesia that accounts for 69%. Patients operated under general anesthesia have maximum post-operative complication rates of 14.5% followed by spinal anesthesia 12.06%

- and local anesthesia 5.37% (p value = 0.00792). The overall anaesthetic complications were 32%. Post-operative nausea and vomiting constituted 55.55% of the total post anaesthesia complications. Other complications were headache (33.33%) and backache (11.11%).
4. Our study had undergone four types of ambulatory procedures Office surgery (29%), Daycare surgeries (29%), Overnight surgeries (12%), short stay surgeries (28%). Extended stay (>72 hours) constituted 2% of the remaining patients.
 5. Post anesthesia drowsiness (28.57%), post-operative nausea and vomiting (28.57%), wound dehiscence (14.2%) and prolonged surgery (28.57%) constitutes as the reason for extended stay(>72hour).
 6. Various procedures including cholecystectomies (8%), inguinal mesh hernioplasty (3%), eversion of sac for hydrocele (7%), breast surgeries (5%), urosurgical procedures (11%), biopsies and FNACs (30%), soft tissue swelling excisions (11%), incision drainage, debridement, secondary suturing , foreign body removal etc.(25%) were performed as a ambulatory procedure during study period.
 7. Open cholecystectomy had post-operative complication rates of 9.09% when compared to that of laparoscopic cholecystectomy that is 5.88%. The total extended stay post cholecystectomy (prolonged surgery, post-operative nausea and vomiting and post-operative surgical site bleeding) of around 80% were found following open cholecystectomy. (p=0.47786)
 8. Mean operating time was 30.34 minutes with standard deviation of 10.72 minutes for ambulatory surgeries. There was no correlation of operating speed with post-operative complications and readmissions in our study. (p= 0.431)
 9. There were 8% of total post-operative complication rates. Only 2.2% of the complications require patients to extend their stay (>72 hours) in the hospital. 68% of the total complications were of surgical complications rest 32% complications accounts for post anesthesia complications. There was no mortality due to any operative/post-operative complications.
 10. Post-operative surgical site pain (35%) and post-operative nausea vomiting (17%) were the major cause of the post-operative complications. Other complications were post-operative bleeding (14%), hematuria (14%), wound dehiscence (4%), headache and backache (13%).
 11. There were 8.6% of the patients who had to extend their hospital stay post-surgery, out of which 74% of the patients were discharged within 72hours of perioperative period and 26% of the patients had to extend their stay more than 72 hours. All of the patients were discharged within 1 week of perioperative period.
 12. The major cause for Delayed discharge (<72hour of hospital stay) was the logistical challenge (43.4%). Rest 17% of the patients were not confident postsurgery to go home and were discharged beyond their planned perioperative period. Other causes were active bleeding (4.34%), prolonged surgery (4.34%), post-surgery observation (13.04%), and change of anaesthesia type (8.69%), pain (4.39%), and hematuria (4.39%).
 13. There was 1% readmission. Wound dehiscence constituted 40% of readmissions.
 14. Rest hematuria, surgical site bleeding, and nausea vomiting constituted 20% each of total readmissions.

Figure 1: Showing Pre-operative ward

Figure 2: showing photographs of post-operative ward

Figure 3: showing upper GI Endoscopy as a office procedure

Figure 4: showing USG guided FNAC under local anaestheisa as an office procedure

Figure 5: debridement of ulcer, pre-operative and post-operative photograph as an office procedure under local anaesthesia

Day Care Surgeries

Figure 6: showing intraoperative photographs of right sided hydrocele, for which eversion of sac was done under local anaesthesia as a day care procedure

Overnight Stay:

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Figure 7: showing pre-operative photograph of phimosis, for which circumcision was done (intraoperative photograph) as an overnight surgery procedure

Figure 8: showing intraoperative and post-operative photographs of mesh hernioplasty done under spinal anaesthesia as an overnight stay procedure

Short Stay Surgeries:

Figure 9: showing pre and post-operative photograph of traumatic non healing ulcer for which Split thickness skin grafting was done under spinal anaesthesia as a short stay procedure

Figure 10: intraoperative photographs of TURP and resected prostatic chips done under spinal anaesthesia as a short stay procedure

Figure 11: showing intraoperative photographs of laparoscopic cholecystectomy done under general anaesthesia as a short stay procedure

Figure 12: post-operative photographs of laparoscopic cholecystectomy and open cholecystectomy

Complications:

Figure 13: post-operative day 01 of laparoscopic cholecystomy showing active drain site bleeding which lead to extended stay of the patient

Figure 14: showing hematuria post TURP leading to extended stay of the patient

Figure 15: post operated case of eversion of sac for hydrocele with surgical site infection and wound dehiscence

Discussion

We had divided the ambulatory procedures on the basis of planned length of hospital stay that were Office Surgeries, Day care Surgeries, Overnight surgeries and short stay surgeries. Office procedure constituted 31%, Daycare 27%, overnight stay 12%, short stay surgeries 28%. And approximately 2% of the patients were those who stayed more than 72 hours in the hospital. Out of total complications, 89% of the complications were taken by the overnight stay and short stay surgery. Day care and office surgery constituted only 7.4% & 3.73% of the complications respectively.

Complication rates were higher for short stay and overnight surgery procedure because of the prolonged procedure and inclusion of spinal and general anaesthesia during procedures. Day care and office surgery patients only required minimal or regional anaesthesia and the procedure were also very limited in severity and due to less exposure, less complication were found. Complications in overnight stay and short surgery were comparable that is 13 and 11 respectively. The p-value, being less than 0.00001 at a significance level of $p < 0.05$, indicates a substantial correlation between surgical

complications for overnight and short-stay procedures compared to office and day care surgeries. Readmission rates were 0% for office surgeries, 1.08% for day care surgeries, 2.32% for overnight surgeries and 3.12% for short stay surgeries. There was no previous study that has included all these criteria. So, there was no obvious comparison of our study to the past.

Various types of surgeries were performed in the setting of ambulatory surgeries ranging from fine needle aspiration cytology to breast surgeries and hepatobiliary surgeries. Biopsies and FNACs accounts for 32% of the total ambulatory surgeries. Urosurgical procedures including SPCs, DJ stent placement and removal, nephrolithomies, cystolithotomies etc. accounts for 11%. Soft tissue swelling including lipoma, sebaceous cysts, epidermal cysts etc. account for 11% of the total procedures. Cholecystectomies including both open and laparoscopic contributes to 7.79%.

Rest, mesh hernioplasty for inguinal hernia (3.63%), incision and drainage, secondary suturing (6.12%), eversion of sac for hydrocele (6.96%), upper GI endoscopy (3.62%) and other minor procedures contributes to 14.48% of ambulatory pro-

cedures. In our study we have observed only 28 patients out of 359 reported with post-operative complications. Around 8% of the complications are significantly better comparative to previous studies. S. kala, et al. in his study observed a total of 10.39% of complications. Out of 8% of complications 5% that is out of 28 patients, 20 had only reported minor complications which was relieved only by symptomatic management and reassurance and did not require extended hospital stay.

Only 2% that is only 7 patients out of 359 patients reported complications that leads to extended hospital stay(>72hours), which is also in coherence to the study done by Surendra Kumar Kala and Sushil Kumar Gupta in NIIMS medical college and hospital Jaipur. They took a data of over 2527 patients and only 2.9% patient required extended hospital stay. 32% of the complications were anaesthetics complications including post-operative nausea and vomiting, headache, drowsiness and backache. Rest 68% of the complications were surgical complications which includes active bleeding, hematuria, surgical site pain and wound dehiscence. [6]

Majority of the complication are of surgical site pain, and post-operative nausea and vomiting (approximately 52% of total complications). Surgical site pain is around 35% of all complications in our study which was similar to study of Scott I. Marshall and Frances Chung. They had also mentioned about post-operative pain constitutes 30% of all complications. Majority of post-operative pain was relieved following using analgesics (oral and intravenous NSAIDS). None of the patient experienced severe pain which led to the extension of his hospital stay. There were no readmissions with complaints of surgical site pain. [7]

Readmission in our study was considered to all patients who had to be admitted in the hospital within 1 week of post ambulatory surgery discharge. Readmissions in our study were experienced by 6 patients which was just over 1% of the total patients. Rest 99% of the patients followed up expectedly. Readmission rates were significantly low as compared to literature. Scott I. Marshall and Frances Chung also observed a readmission rate of approximately 1% in their study. He mentioned about post-surgical bleeding and post-operative pain as the major criteria for admission. In our study as well 50% of the readmission was due to bleeding (surgical site bleeding & hematuria). Rest

33.33% of patients were readmitted due to wound dehiscence and 1 patient was readmitted due to Nausea and Vomiting. All the readmitted patients were discharged within 1 week of hospital stay. [7]

Conclusion

The study explores the feasibility, benefits, and complications of ambulatory surgeries at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital. Overall, there was no mortality; only 2% of the complications lead extended stay. 99% of the patients recovered well at their home with only 1% patient's required readmission post ambulatory surgery. Patient selection criteria, presence of responsible caregiver, far off distance from the hospital can be concluded as the limitation of this study. Thus, we conclude ambulatory surgeries are safe, beneficial and feasible and better save many resources of the patient and the overburdened Indian hospitals. There is further much room to explore new patient selection protocols, minimal invasive surgical techniques, regional anaesthesia, and setting of new protocols and separate multidisciplinary teams to tackle all the perioperative barriers.

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